

eDhanvantari: Revolutionizing Healthcare with a Cloud-Based EHR Platform

Authors: Sahasrabuddhe Mandar S., Sahasrabuddhe Sneha M., Yengul Roshan S., Gokhale Gauri A.

Abstract

This white paper explores the transformative impact of eDhanvantari, a cloud-based, lightweight Electronic Health Record (EHR) platform designed specifically for healthcare professionals in India. With its web and mobile applications, customizable case-papers, telehealth support, and integration with the Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission, eDhanvantari is leading the way in making medical practices paper-free and efficient. This paper discusses the key features and benefits of eDhanvantari and highlights its recognition as the "MEITY-NASSCOM Startup Women Entrepreneur Award – Healthcare" in 2019. It also explores how the integration with Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission further enhances its value in improving healthcare services in India.

Introduction

In today's fast-paced healthcare landscape, digital innovation is crucial to optimize patient care and streamline administrative processes. eDhanvantari, a cloud-based EHR platform, offers a comprehensive solution tailored to the unique needs of doctors and healthcare professionals in India. This white paper aims to shed light on the functionalities and advantages of eDhanvantari, showcasing its role in transforming medical practices.

Key Features

Web and Mobile Applications: eDhanvantari provides healthcare professionals with the convenience of accessing patient records and managing clinical tasks through both web and mobile applications. This ensures seamless access to critical information regardless of location, enhancing productivity and enabling remote consultations.

Role-Based Access: With role-based access control, eDhanvantari offers different levels of access to various stakeholders involved in the healthcare ecosystem, including clinicians, receptionists, clinic managers, patients, and opticians. This feature ensures data security and privacy while enabling efficient collaboration among different healthcare professionals.

Customizable Case-Papers: eDhanvantari empowers doctors to create customized case-papers, allowing them to tailor patient records according to their specific requirements. This feature enhances the efficiency of documentation, simplifies information retrieval, and improves the overall quality of patient care.

Telehealth Support: The inclusion of telehealth support enables healthcare professionals to offer remote consultations and extend their services beyond traditional clinical settings. eDhanvantari facilitates seamless audio and video communication, empowering doctors to connect with patients remotely and provide timely medical advice.

Industry Recognition

In 2019, eDhanvantari was awarded the prestigious “**MeitY-NASSCOM Startup Women Entrepreneur Awards 2019**” in the **Healthcare Segment**, highlighting its exceptional contribution to the healthcare sector. This recognition serves as a testament to the platform's innovation, user-friendliness, and impact on improving healthcare delivery in India. The eDhanvantari success story inspires other entrepreneurs, particularly women, to drive transformation in the healthcare industry.

Integration with Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission

eDhanvantari's on-going integration with the Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission further solidifies its significance in the Indian healthcare landscape. By aligning with this national initiative, eDhanvantari actively contributes to the government's vision of providing accessible, affordable, and high-quality healthcare to all citizens. The integration enhances the interoperability and data exchange capabilities of eDhanvantari, ensuring seamless connectivity with the wider healthcare ecosystem.

In addition to this, ABDM integration will also ensure that all healthcare professionals using eDhanvantari will be incentivized based on the health records that they capture in the system annually.

Benefits and Future Potential

The adoption of eDhanvantari brings several benefits to healthcare professionals and patients alike. It eliminates the burden of manual paperwork, reduces errors, and enables efficient management of patient records. The platform's telehealth support promotes convenient access to healthcare services, particularly in remote areas. As eDhanvantari continues to evolve, it has the potential to revolutionize the healthcare landscape by leveraging emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and data analytics.

Conclusion

eDhanvantari stands as a robust and user-friendly EHR platform designed for doctors and healthcare professionals in India. Its web and mobile applications, customizable case-papers,

telehealth support, and integration with the Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission position it as a key player in the digital transformation of the healthcare sector. With its recognition by the "MeitY-NASSCOM Startup Women Entrepreneur Awards 2019" and a commitment to innovation, eDhanvantari has the potential to drive significant improvements in patient care, efficiency, and accessibility throughout the country.